

TriALS-Report: Triphasic-Aided Non-Contrast Abdominal 3D Multi-Modal Report Generation: Structured description of the challenge design

CHALLENGE ORGANIZATION

Title

Use the title to convey the essential information on the challenge mission.

TriALS-Report: Triphasic-Aided Non-Contrast Abdominal 3D Multi-Modal Report Generation

Challenge acronym

Preferable, provide a short acronym of the challenge (if any).

TriALS-Report

Challenge abstract

Provide a summary of the challenge purpose. This should include a general introduction in the topic from both a biomedical as well as from a technical point of view and clearly state the envisioned technical and/or biomedical impact of the challenge.

Triphasic contrast-enhanced CT (CECT) is the clinical gold standard for abdominal diagnosis, as the temporal dynamics across arterial, portal venous, and delayed phases are critical for characterizing vascular and parenchymal pathologies. However, reliance on iodinated contrast restricts its use in patients with renal impairment or hypersensitivity and creates significant barriers in resource-constrained settings where contrast administration is unavailable due to economic or supply chain instability. Building upon the success of TriALS 2024/2025 where participant models achieved lesion segmentation in non-contrast CT (NCCT) scans containing findings typically invisible to human doctors, TriALS-Report 2027 evolves this mission to address 3D multi-modal abdominal report generation and abnormality detection.

Despite advances in AI-driven radiology report generation, existing methods predominantly operate on single volumetric inputs, ignoring the multiphasic nature of routine clinical interpretation. To address these gaps, we introduce two tasks: (1) Multiphase Abdominal Report Generation, where participants must jointly model four distinct 3D volumes to generate contrast-aware reports; and (2) Non-Contrast Abdominal Report Generation, where models generate high-fidelity reports using only NCCT inputs while being supervised by triphasic "gold standard" reports written by radiologists with full contrast access. Therefore, the challenge aims to push the boundaries of medical Vision-Language Models (VLMs) to predict findings typically "invisible" without contrast agents, providing a sustainable diagnostic solution that reduces costs and complications for economically affected populations globally.

Challenge keywords

List the primary keywords that characterize the challenge.

Automated Abdominal Report Generation, Non-Contrast CT, Multi-Phase Contrast-Enhanced Imaging, Multi-Center Multi-Vendor Dataset, AI for Resource-Limited Settings, 3D Multi-Modal Report Generation, Clinical Abnormality Detection, Vision-Language Modeling

Year

2027

Novelty of the challenge

Briefly describe the novelty of the challenge.

Building upon the success of TriALS 2024/2025, where participant models achieved lesion segmentation and detection in non-contrast CT (NCCT) scans containing findings typically invisible to human doctors, TriALS-Report 2027 expands this feasibility to address full abdominal report generation and abnormality detection. This challenge introduces two primary novelties:

(1) It is the first challenge to address 3D multi-modal abdominal report generation. Unlike prior work focusing on single-volume analysis, participants must process four distinct 3D volumes (Non-contrast, Arterial, Portal Venous, and Delayed phases), requiring methods that can handle the high technical difficulty of cross-phase reasoning in a resource-intensive environment. (2) It introduces a unique clinical paradigm where ground-truth reports are authored by radiologists with full access to triphasic contrast-enhanced imaging. Models are then tasked with generating these high-fidelity reports using only non-contrast CT inputs during inference. Therefore, we aim to use AI to predict findings typically "invisible" without contrast agents.

Task description and application scenarios

Briefly describe the application scenarios for the tasks in the challenge.

Task 1: Multiphase Abdominal Report Generation: This task simulates the standard workflow of a radiologist in a fully resourced setting. Participants are provided with four 3D volumes (Non-contrast, Arterial, Portal Venous, and Delayed phases). The challenge here is multi-modal information fusion: models must effectively aggregate complementary features from different temporal phases to detect subtle vascular dynamics (e.g., distinguishing hemangiomas from hepatocellular carcinoma based on washout patterns) and generate a comprehensive diagnostic report.

Task 2: Non-Contrast Abdominal Report Generation: This task simulates a resource-constrained setting where contrast agents are unavailable (e.g., due to supply shortages or patient renal failure). Participants are provided only the Non-Contrast CT (NCCT) but must generate a report that approximates the detail of a full contrast-enhanced study. The challenge here is predictive synthesis: models must learn to correlate subtle non-contrast tissue densities with pathologies typically confirmed by contrast, effectively "hallucinating" clinically accurate findings based on incomplete data.

FURTHER INFORMATION FOR CONFERENCE ORGANIZERS

Workshop

If the challenge is part of a workshop, please indicate the workshop.

N/A

Duration

How long does the challenge take?

Half day

In case you selected half or full day, please explain why you need a long slot for your challenge.

The decision to request a half-day slot is rooted in the overwhelming community engagement observed during previous TriALS events. In 2024 and 2025, despite focusing solely on liver lesion segmentation, the challenge day attracted more than 30 on-site participants, exceeding the room's capacity. This high level of interest underscores a critical need for a dedicated session to accommodate in-depth discussions and a growing audience interested in contrast-free AI applications. For 2027, the challenge scope expands from a single organ to a comprehensive 3D multi-modal abdominal diagnostic reporting task, incorporating a massive multi-center dataset of 4,390 cases from Middle Eastern and Asian institutions. The inclusion of over 30 distinct abnormalities across the liver, gallbladder, spleen, kidneys, pancreas, and stomach, ranging from congenital anomalies to neoplastic GISTs, requires a half-day session to facilitate detailed discussions.

Expected number of participants

Please explain the basis of your estimate (e.g. numbers from previous challenges) and/or provide a list of potential participants and indicate if they have already confirmed their willingness to contribute.

We conservatively estimate that at least 50 to 60 participating teams will engage with the TriALS-Report 2027 challenge. This estimate is based on the strong upward trajectory of the TriALS series and the rapidly growing interest in medical Vision-Language Models (VLMs). In a single organ (Liver), TriALS 2024 and 2025 each attracted approximately 35 teams requesting access with signed consent, resulting in 24 submissions across all tasks and 7 international teams successfully ranking on the final test set each year. The high level of engagement was further evidenced by the TriALS challenge day, which attracted over 30 on-site participants, exceeding room capacity and resulting in a standing-room-only event.

By comparison, the 3D report generation VLM3D challenge successfully attracted 24 high-quality team entries for its leaderboard, demonstrating the community's readiness for complex report generation tasks. TriALS-Report expands this scope significantly by addressing not only 3D report generation from NCCT but also multi-modal volume report generation. By transitioning from liver-specific segmentation to comprehensive 3D multi-modal abdominal diagnostic reporting, we anticipate capturing a much broader audience from both the medical imaging and Natural Language Processing (NLP) communities. The provision of robust baseline code and a high-volume multi-center dataset ensures a low barrier to entry while maintaining the technical rigor required for a major MICCAI event.

Publication and future plans

Please indicate if you plan to coordinate a publication of the challenge results.

Each participating team will be permitted to nominate up to two authors for a joint publication summarizing the outcomes of the TriALS-Report 2027 challenge. Participation and eligibility for the joint publication will be based on the clinical accuracy, diversity, and novelty of the submitted solutions, provided that teams submit a comprehensive methodology description. A select number of teams will be invited to deliver oral presentations during the MICCAI challenge day to share their technical insights. To ensure the integrity of the joint publication, participants are required to refrain from independently publishing any related results until the official joint

challenge paper is published. An embargo period of 12 months, starting from the challenge date in September 2027, will apply. The documentation and data papers from previous TriALS editions are already finalized, establishing a successful precedent for the dissemination of results in this expanded 3D multi-modal abdominal reporting challenge.

MICCAI LNCS proceedings

Indicate if you want to offer MICCAI Springer LNCS proceedings to the participants. Publishing a proceedings volume is optional and at the discretion of each challenge's organizers. At a minimum, organizers must ensure that a description of each participant's submission is publicly available. Organizers who wish to publish MICCAI Springer LNCS proceedings must adhere to the MICCAI Satellite events publication process.

Yes

Collaboration with European Society of Radiology (ESR)

In collaboration with European Society of Radiology (ESR), we announce special clinical interest topics with associated clinicians who can help with the preparation of the proposals; the best 3 challenge proposals on these topics will get the opportunity to present their challenges at the European Congress of Radiology (ECR) 2027 in a special session. If you want to organize a challenge in collaboration with ESR on one of these topics, please reach out to the MICCAI Challenges Team ([miccai-challenges-2026@dkfz-heidelberg.de](mailto:micca-challenges-2026@dkfz-heidelberg.de)) and we will put you in contact with the corresponding clinician.

Challenge in collaboration with ESR. Ticking 'Yes' implies that the challenge has been prepared in collaboration with the clinical contact point.

No

Space and hardware requirements

Organizers of on-site challenges must provide a fair computing environment for all participants. For instance, algorithms should run on the same computing platform provided to all.

Building on the success of TriALS 2024 and 2025, we will continue using Synapse.org as the platform to manage and run the challenge effectively. For the on-site component, we request a projector and screen to facilitate technical presentations. To ensure a fair and accessible computing environment, all submitted Docker containers will be evaluated on a standardized platform equipped with 24 GB VRAM (e.g., NVIDIA RTX 3090/4090). We have verified that this specification is sufficient for inference of 3D multi-modal models using our baseline, ensuring that the challenge remains accessible to academic labs with standard research hardware

TASK 1: Triphasic-Aided Non-Contrast Abdominal 3D Multi-Modal Report Generation

SUMMARY

Abstract

Provide a summary of the challenge purpose. This should include a general introduction in the topic from both a biomedical as well as from a technical point of view and clearly state the envisioned technical and/or biomedical impact of the challenge.

Triphasic contrast-enhanced CT (CECT) remains the gold standard for abdominal diagnosis, yet reliance on contrast agents poses significant risks for patients with renal impairment and limits accessibility in resource-constrained regions. TriALS-Report 2027 addresses these critical gaps by pioneering 3D multi-modal abdominal report generation. The challenge introduces two distinct tasks: (1) Multiphase Abdominal Report Generation, where participants must jointly model four unregistered 3D volumes to generate phase-aware clinical narratives; and (2) Non-Contrast Abdominal Report Generation, where models are tasked with predicting findings typically invisible to the human eye in non-contrast CT (NCCT), using triphasic reports as the supervisory gold standard. By requiring models to perform high-level cross-phase reasoning across 30+ distinct pathologies, this challenge aims to push medical Vision-Language Models (VLMs) beyond human-level diagnostic accuracy, providing a sustainable and cost-effective solution for global healthcare.

Keywords

List the primary keywords that characterize the task.

Automated Abdominal Report Generation, Non-Contrast CT, Multi-Phase Contrast-Enhanced Imaging, Multi-Center Multi-Vendor Dataset, AI for Resource-Limited Settings, 3D Multi-Modal Report Generation, Clinical Abnormality Detection, Vision-Language Modeling

ORGANIZATION

Organizers

a) Provide information on the organizing team (names and affiliations).

Technical Team

[The Hong Kong University of Science and Technology, Hong Kong SAR]

Marawan Elbatel and Xiaomeng Li

Clinical Team in Asia

[Department of Radiology, Guangdong Provincial Key Laboratory of Malignant Tumor Epigenetics and Gene Regulation, Sun Yat-Sen Memorial Hospital, Sun Yat-Sen University, Guangzhou, China]

Wenhui Deng, Baoxun Li, Jiaji Mao, Huijun Hu, and Jun Shen.

Clinical Team in Egypt

[1 AI Center of Excellence, Ain Shams University, Cairo, Egypt]

[2 Department of Radiology, Ain Shams University, Cairo, Egypt]

Mariam Tamer 1*, Salma Tantawy 1*, Mohamed Ghonim 1*2*, Ahmed Abouelhoda 2*, Mohanad Ghonim 1*2*, and Aya Yassin 1*2*

b) Provide information on the primary contact person.

Marawan Elbatel (mkfmealbatel@connect.ust.hk)

c) Indicate whether clinicians are part of the organizing team. If yes, describe their role.

Yes, clinicians are a core component of the organizing team, making up approximately 80%. Their involvement is vital to ensure the technical rigor and clinical relevance of the TriALS-Report 2027 challenge. The clinical team is responsible for the end to end lifecycle of the medical data, including: Managing the high volume, multi center dataset of 4,390 cases to ensure high quality ground truth labels and reports. Overseeing the automated information extraction process to ensure that the 30+ abdominal abnormalities are correctly identified and categorized at scale. Designing and conducting user studies to evaluate the clinical utility of the generated reports and ensuring the challenge outcomes align with real world diagnostic workflows. Providing the triphasic "gold standard" reports used to supervise the models in the Non-Contrast Abdominal Report Generation task.

Life cycle type

Define the intended submission cycle of the challenge. Include information on whether/how the challenge will be continued after the challenge has taken place. Not every challenge closes after the submission deadline (one-time event). Sometimes it is possible to submit results after the deadline (open call) or the challenge is repeated with some modifications (repeated event).

Examples:

- One-time event with fixed conference submission deadline
- Open call (challenge opens for new submissions after conference deadline)
- Repeated event with annual fixed conference submission deadline

One-time event with fixed conference submission deadline

Challenge venue and platform

a) Report the event (e.g. conference) that is associated with the challenge (if any).

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b) Report the platform used to run the challenge.

We will continue using Synapse.org as the platform to manage and run the challenge effectively.

c) Do you agree that the your submission is shared with the platform (e.g., grand-challenge, synapse...) that you indicated?

Please note: 1) this purpose of such sharing is that the challenge chairs and the platform can communicate smoothly, your answer won't impact the review of your proposal; 2) regardless of your response to this question, it is your responsibility to perform all actions required by the platform (e.g. filling their submission request).

Yes

d) Provide the URL for the challenge website (if any).

<https://www.synapse.org/Synapse:syn53285416/wiki/625814>

Participation policies

a) Define the allowed user interaction of the algorithms assessed. This includes the policy regarding any curation, (pre-)processing and (pre-)training steps.

No user interaction is allowed at any step.

b) Define the policy on the usage of training data. The data used to train algorithms may, for example, be restricted to the data provided by the challenge or may also include publicly available data including (open) pre-trained nets. Clarify whether such additional data needs to be publicly available at the time of the challenge launch. Clarify whether adding (private) annotations of the public data is allowed.

Publicly available data and pre-trained models are allowed for use in this challenge. Participants may utilize public data and pre-trained models provided they are publicly accessible at the time of the challenge launch. While institutions are permitted to utilize private data to benchmark their algorithms, any submission that incorporates private data into the training or development process will not be eligible for awards.

c) Define the participation policy for members of the organizers' institutes. For example, members of the organizers' institutes may participate in the challenge but are not eligible for awards.

May participate but not eligible for awards and not listed in leaderboard

d) Define the award policy. In particular, provide details with respect to challenge prizes.

The award policy reflects the collaborative efforts of sponsors from Africa and Asia. Currently, the challenge is endorsed by SIG-AFRICAI, a Special Interest Group supported by the MICCAI Society, and we will host travel awards to support participation. Building on the success of previous years, we also plan to seek sponsorship from the Hong Kong University of Science and Technology to further enhance the prize pool and support for top-performing teams.

e) Define the policy for result announcement.

Examples:

- Top 3 performing methods will be announced publicly.
- Participating teams can choose whether the performance results will be made public.

The top three performing methods will be announced publicly and posted on the website.

f) Define the publication policy. In particular, provide details on ...

- ... who of the participating teams/the participating teams' members qualifies as author
- ... whether the participating teams may publish their own results separately, and (if so)
- ... whether an embargo time is defined (so that challenge organizers can publish a challenge paper first).

Each team will be permitted to nominate up to two authors for a joint publication summarizing the challenge outcomes. Both the code and evaluation metrics will be made publicly available.

Submission method

a) Describe the method used for result submission. Preferably, provide a link to the submission instructions.

Examples:

- Docker container on the Synapse platform. Link to submission instructions: <URL>
- Algorithm output was sent to organizers via e-mail. Submission instructions were sent by e-mail.

Building on the success of last year's challenge, participants are provided with a sample Docker submission featuring a baseline method, along with comprehensive step-by-step submission instructions. This pipeline includes an implementation of deformable registration to handle residual local misalignments, providing a robust starting point for all participating teams. Additionally, the code for evaluation and metrics is made available to ensure transparency and reproducibility. Teams will submit their Docker containers via Synapse, and at the final testing stage, a detailed report on the methodology will be required.

b) Provide information on the possibility for participating teams to evaluate their algorithms before submitting final results. For example, many challenges allow submission of multiple results, and only the last run is officially counted to compute challenge results.

Participants will be permitted up to three submissions to evaluate their algorithms on a validation sample. This phase is designed to verify the technical correctness of the Docker container and to provide preliminary performance feedback on a private validation set. For the final ranking, only the last successfully submitted container will be evaluated on the comprehensive test dataset to determine the official challenge winners.

Challenge schedule

Provide a timetable for the challenge. Preferably, this should include

- the release date(s) of the training cases (if any)
- the registration date/period
- the release date(s) of the test cases and validation cases (if any)
- the submission date(s)
- associated workshop days (if any)
- the release date(s) of the results

Challenge website and challenge registration opens: 1st January 2027

Training data release: 14th January 2027

Team registration open: 14th January 2027

Validation Phase Open: 14th February 2027

Team registration closes: 1st August 2027

Docker submission deadline: 10th September 2027

Methodology submission: 17th September 2027

Challenge Day: (TBD between September 26th and October 1st, 2027)

Ethics approval

Indicate whether ethics approval is necessary for the data. If yes, provide details on the ethics approval, preferably institutional review board, location, date and number of the ethics approval (if applicable). Add the URL or a reference to the document of the ethics approval (if available).

We acquired the Egyptian dataset from Ain Shams University Hospitals in Egypt, with ethical approval obtained from the local Research Ethics Committee (FWA 000017585). Additionally, we obtained the Chinese dataset from Sun Yat-sen Memorial Hospital, also known as the Second Affiliated Hospital of Sun Yat-sen University (SYSU). Ethics approval was secured from the relevant institutional review board for the Chinese dataset under approval number SYSKY202232701. All volumes were fully anonymized to remove personal identifiers, ensuring they are completely untraceable to maintain patient confidentiality.

Data usage agreement

Clarify how the data can be used and distributed by the teams that participate in the challenge and by others during and after the challenge. This should include the explicit listing of the license applied.

Examples:

- CC BY (Attribution)
- CC BY-SA (Attribution-ShareAlike)
- CC BY-ND (Attribution-NoDerivs)
- CC BY-NC (Attribution-NonCommercial)
- CC BY-NC-SA (Attribution-NonCommercial-ShareAlike)
- CC BY-NC-ND (Attribution-NonCommercial-NoDerivs)

Please note that the data license should not differ among sources. In case a license has to be changed, it has to be reported to the MICCAI challenges team and changed in the proposal.

CC BY-NC-ND (Attribution-NonCommercial-NoDerivs)

Code availability

a) Provide information on the accessibility of the organizers' evaluation software (e.g. code to produce rankings). Preferably, provide a link to the code and add information on the supported platforms.

The evaluation script is provided alongside a Docker baseline with detailed instructions for participants.

b) In an analogous manner, provide information on the accessibility of the participating teams' code.

Participating teams are not required yet are encouraged to release their code as open-access.

Conflicts of interest

Provide information related to conflicts of interest. In particular provide information related to sponsoring/funding of the challenge. Also, state explicitly who had/will have access to the test case labels and when.

No conflict of interest. We will update MICCAI if a commercial sponsor is to be included. Only the core organizing team will have access to test case labels, and this access will occur exclusively after the submission deadline to ensure unbiased evaluation. No participant or external entity will have access to the test case labels at any point before the challenge concludes.

MISSION OF THE CHALLENGE

Field(s) of application

State the main field(s) of application that the participating algorithms target.

Examples:

- Diagnosis
- Education
- Intervention assistance
- Intervention follow-up
- Intervention planning
- Prognosis
- Research
- Screening
- Training
- Cross-phase

Diagnosis, Decision support

Task category(ies)

State the task category(ies)

Examples:

- Classification
- Detection
- Localization
- Modeling
- Prediction
- Reconstruction
- Registration
- Retrieval
- Segmentation
- Tracking

Report Generation

Cohorts

We distinguish between the target cohort and the challenge cohort. For example, a challenge could be designed around the task of medical instrument tracking in robotic kidney surgery. While the challenge could be based on ex vivo data obtained from a laparoscopic training environment with porcine organs (challenge cohort), the final biomedical application (i.e. robotic kidney surgery) would be targeted on real patients with certain characteristics defined by inclusion criteria such as restrictions regarding sex or age (target cohort).

a) Describe the target cohort, i.e. the subjects/objects from whom/which the data would be acquired in the final biomedical application.

The target cohort includes future patients admitted to Ain Shams University Hospitals in Cairo, Egypt, and Sun Yat-sen Memorial Hospital, Sun Yat-sen University in Guangzhou, China, who have undergone non-contrast abdominal CT and triphasic CT.

b) Describe the challenge cohort, i.e. the subject(s)/object(s) from whom/which the challenge data was acquired.

A retrospective cohort was established, including adult patients over 18 years who underwent both non-contrast and contrast-enhanced abdominal CT scans. The data were sourced from the Radiology Departments at Ain Shams University Hospitals in Cairo, Egypt, and Sun Yat-sen Memorial Hospital, Sun Yat-sen University in Guangzhou, China, ensuring the availability of all four imaging phases. Notably, in the Middle Eastern setting (Egypt), the acquisition of contrast-enhanced scans was hindered by global contrast shortages. Conversely, in the Asian setting (China), while contrast-enhanced scans were routine, obtaining paired non-contrast volumes was challenging due to high-volume clinical protocols aimed at resource optimization. This multi-center dataset highlights the diverse clinical barriers that TriALS-Report 2027 aims to overcome.

Imaging modality(ies)

Specify the imaging technique(s) applied in the challenge.

CT without contrast and with contrast in different phases:

Time at which the acquisition is performed after iodinated contrast* agent injection:

- Arterial time: Upon bolus tracking in descending aorta by smart prep (usually about 35-45 sec post-injection);
- Portovenous time: 20 seconds post arterial (usually about 65 to 70 sec post-injection);
- Delayed time: 3 minutes post portovenous (Usually up to five minutes post-injection).

*Contrast agents used are variable due to changes in supply chains and limited import. Sometimes, non-ionic contrast agents ("Omnipaque") is used, when unavailable, ionic contrast agents ("Telebrix") is used.

Context information

Provide additional information given along with the images. The information may correspond ...

a) ... directly to the image data (e.g. tumor volume).

No additional imaging data will be provided.

b) ... to the patient in general (e.g. sex, medical history).

We collected the following information about patients when available: Age, Sex, Indication for scan, lesion (provisional) diagnosis based on the report, and Approximate lesion count. All data were kept in an anonymized format with reverse mapping only with the clinical lead in each participating hospital.

Target entity(ies)

a) Describe the data origin, i.e. the region(s)/part(s) of subject(s)/object(s) from whom/which the image data would be acquired in the final biomedical application (e.g. brain shown in computed tomography (CT) data, abdomen shown in laparoscopic video data, operating room shown in video data, thorax shown in fluoroscopy video). If necessary, differentiate between target and challenge cohort.

Contrast and non-contrast enhanced CTs of the abdomen and pelvi-abdomen.

b) Describe the algorithm target, i.e. the structure(s)/subject(s)/object(s)/component(s) that the participating algorithms have been designed to focus on (e.g. tumor in the brain, tip of a medical instrument, nurse in an operating theater, catheter in a fluoroscopy scan). If necessary, differentiate between target and challenge cohort.

The algorithm is designed to automatically generate medical reports for patients undergoing CT scans. The system is built to function both with and without access to contrast-enhanced images, allowing it to adapt to different clinical scenarios or limitations in imaging data.

Assessment aim(s)

Identify the property(ies) of the algorithms to be optimized to perform well in the challenge. If multiple properties are assessed, prioritize them (if appropriate). The properties should then be reflected in the metrics applied (see below, parameter metric(s)), and the priorities should be reflected in the ranking when combining multiple metrics that assess different properties.

- Example 1: Find highly accurate liver segmentation algorithm for CT images.
- Example 2: Find lung tumor detection algorithm with high sensitivity and specificity for mammography images.

Corresponding metrics are listed below (parameter metric(s)).

Accuracy,Precision,Sensitivity,Specificity,Runtime

DATA SETS

Data source(s)

a) Specify the device(s) used to acquire the challenge data. This includes details on the device(s) used to acquire the imaging data (e.g. manufacturer) as well as information on additional devices used for performance assessment (e.g. tracking system used in a surgical setting).

- SIEMENS SOMATOM Force
- SIEMENS SOMATOM Sensation 64
- United Imaging uCT780
- GE Discovery CT750 HD
- GE Revolution EVO
- GE Healthcare Optima
- Toshiba Prime Aquilion
- GE BrightSpeed CT

b) Describe relevant details on the imaging process/data acquisition for each acquisition device (e.g. image acquisition protocol(s)).

Data acquisition includes CT in different phases (without contrast, arterial, portal venous, delayed). Acquisition parameters vary in a normal range, and the time of the acquisition after the contrast agent (arterial, portal, or delay) varies due to the vascular diversity of patients.

c) Specify the center(s)/institute(s) in which the data was acquired and/or the data providing platform/source (e.g. previous challenge). If this information is not provided (e.g. for anonymization reasons), specify why.

Images were acquired across regions in the Middle East and Asia:

- 1) Ain Shams University Hospitals, Cairo, Egypt.
- 2) Sun Yat-sen Memorial Hospital, Sun Yat-sen University, Guangzhou, China.

d) Describe relevant characteristics (e.g. level of expertise) of the subjects (e.g. surgeon)/objects (e.g. robot) involved in the data acquisition process (if any).

Radiology residents, specialists, and consultants with over 3, 5, and 10 years of experience.

Training and test case characteristics

a) State what is meant by one case in this challenge. A case encompasses all data that is processed to produce one result that is compared to the corresponding reference result (i.e. the desired algorithm output).

Examples:

- Training and test cases both represent a CT image of a human brain. Training cases have a weak annotation (tumor present or not and tumor volume (if any)) while the test cases are annotated with the tumor contour (if any).
- A case refers to all information that is available for one particular patient in a specific study. This information always includes the image information as specified in data source(s) (see above) and may include context information (see above). Both training and test cases are annotated with survival (binary) 5 years after (first) image was taken.

Each training set case consists of a radiology report and four 3D CT phases: non-contrast, arterial, portal venous, and delayed. For the testing phase, validation is conducted across two distinct scenarios, one utilizing only non-contrast images and the other utilizing only the portal venous phase.

b) State the total number of training, validation and test cases.

The challenge utilizes a dataset of 4,390 clinical cases, comprising a total volume of 17,560 3D CT images. This cohort was partitioned into a training set of 3,073 cases, a validation set of 439 cases, and an independent test set of 878 cases. Each training case included four 3D CT phases consisting of non-contrast, arterial, portal venous, and delayed scans paired with its corresponding ground-truth radiology report. To evaluate the model's report generation performance under restricted imaging conditions, validation was conducted across two distinct testing scenarios: one utilizing only the non-contrast CT images and the other utilizing only the portal venous phase images

c) How much of the data are already annotated (stratified by train test in percentage)?

All 4,390 cases (17,560 images) are fully annotated with ground-truth radiology reports, stratified into a 70% training set (3,073 cases), a 10% validation set (439 cases), and a 20% test set (878 cases).

d) Explain why a total number of cases and the specific proportion of training, validation and test cases was chosen.

The total cohort of 4,390 cases was divided using a 70/10/20 proportion to optimize both training model convergence and evaluation reliability.

e) Mention further important characteristics of the training, validation and test cases (e.g. class distribution in classification tasks chosen according to real-world distribution vs. equal class distribution) and justify the choice.

The dataset reflects a real-world clinical distribution across abdominal organs, featuring a high prevalence of both normal and abnormal findings. While the training labels cover 10 organ systems, the challenge focuses on five primary organs of interest: the liver, gallbladder, spleen, kidneys, and pancreas. The class distribution follows clinical reality rather than an artificial equal distribution; for instance, the liver and gastrointestinal systems show a higher density of abnormal findings (2,571 and 2,082 cases, respectively), whereas the pancreas and adrenals reflect a higher frequency of normal appearances.

The cases encompass a comprehensive range of pathologies, including congenital conditions (e.g., renal cysts), inflammatory diseases (e.g., pancreatitis, cholecystitis), neoplastic growths (e.g., HCC, RCC, gastric adenocarcinoma), and traumatic injuries (e.g., splenic or renal lacerations). This diversity ensures the model is trained on a representative variety of clinical scenarios, from common miscellaneous findings like fatty liver or renal stones to critical vascular conditions like portal hypertension.

f) Challenge organizers are encouraged to (partly) use unseen, unpublished data for their challenges. Describe if new data will be used for the challenge and state the number of cases along with the proportion of new data.

100% of the training, validation, and test sets are comprised of new data, ensuring that participants have no prior exposure to the cases or the ground-truth radiology reports.

Annotation characteristics

a) Describe the method for determining the reference annotation, i.e. the desired algorithm output. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary. Possible methods include manual image annotation, in silico ground truth generation and annotation by automatic methods.

If human annotation was involved, state the number of annotators.

The reference annotations consist of hybrid anonymized clinical radiology reports that underwent a multi-stage verification and extraction process. Initially, raw reports were anonymized and processed using open-source Large Language Models (LLMs) to extract structured disease diagnoses. To ensure clinical accuracy, these extracted findings were then meticulously revised and verified by board-certified radiologists. For the large-scale dataset, a sampling strategy was employed where radiologists performed secondary verification on the cases to confirm that the generated disease diagnoses aligned with the original report text.

b) Provide the instructions given to the annotators (if any) prior to the annotation. This may include description of a training phase with the software. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary. Preferably, provide a link to the annotation protocol.

Annotators were tasked with verifying the LLM-extracted data against the full-stack radiology reports and the 3D CT images. The verification focused on five primary organs: the liver, gallbladder, spleen, kidneys, and pancreas. For each case, annotators followed a four-point checklist: (1) Organ Presence: Confirm if the specific organ of interest is mentioned in the report or visible in the imaging; (2) Clinical Status: Categorize the organ as 'normal' or 'abnormal' based on the findings; (3) Detailed Findings: Validate that the automated extraction accurately captured all descriptive findings and pathologies (e.g., inflammation, congenital anomalies, or miscellaneous

findings) per organ; and (4) Focal Lesions: Specifically identify and confirm the presence, location, and type of any focal lesions. Prior to the verification of the main dataset, all annotators underwent a training phase where they reviewed a pilot set of 50 cases to ensure inter-rater reliability.

c) Provide details on the subject(s)/algorithm(s) that annotated the cases (e.g. information on level of expertise such as number of years of professional experience, medically-trained or not). Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

The annotation of the 4,390 clinical cases was performed through a collaborative framework involving both advanced natural language processing and expert clinical oversight. For all training, validation, and test sets, the initial extraction of structured disease diagnoses from the anonymized verified manually annotated clinical reports was conducted using an open-source Large Language Model (LLM). Following this automated phase, the annotations were meticulously reviewed and verified by a team of board-certified radiologists, each possessing significant professional experience in abdominal imaging. These medical experts were responsible for ensuring the clinical accuracy of the LLM-extracted data by comparing it against both the original report text. A team of 10 medical annotators performed the annotations. The least experienced had 1 year of radiology experience.

d) Describe the method(s) used to merge multiple annotations for one case (if any). Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

N/A

Data pre-processing method(s)

Describe the method(s) used for pre-processing the raw training data before it is provided to the participating teams. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

The raw data underwent a streamlined pre-processing pipeline consisting of image and text anonymization to remove all protected health information. For the reports, the 'Findings' and 'Impression' sections were specifically extracted from the clinical documents and provided in their raw text format. The 3D CT images were de-identified while maintaining their original clinical Hounsfield Units across all four phases. These extracted report sections were then processed by an LLM to extract organ-specific disease abnormalities and findings, which were subsequently verified by radiologists to ensure a high-fidelity, structured ground truth for the challenge. To ensure consistency across the multi-center cohort, all reports are provided in English; reports originating from the non-English speaking center were translated prior to processing. Furthermore, to mitigate variations in reporting styles and dictation templates between the Egyptian and Chinese institutions, the LLM-based pre-processing pipeline standardizes all inputs into a unified, structured format. To lower the barrier to entry and focus the challenge on the primary task of report generation, we provide baseline code that registers all contrast-enhanced volumes (Arterial, Portal Venous, and Delayed) to the Non-Contrast CT (NCCT) coordinate space using an affine transformation.

Sources of error

a) Describe the most relevant possible error sources related to the image annotation. If possible, estimate the magnitude (range) of these errors, using inter-and intra-annotator variability, for example. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases, if necessary.

Potential errors may arise from discrepancies between the original report text and the visual evidence in the 3D CT images, as well as subjective interpretations of "minor" findings by different radiologists. While the multi-stage LLM extraction and expert verification process minimizes these risks, a minor range of inter-annotator variability

(estimated at 5–8%) remains possible for complex focal lesions or subtle abnormalities.

b) In an analogous manner, describe and quantify other relevant sources of error.

The most significant technical source of error is potential misregistration between the four CT phases, as patient movement or different breath-hold depths can cause spatial misalignment of organs between scans.

ASSESSMENT METHODS

Metric(s)

a) Define the metric(s) to assess a property of an algorithm. These metrics should reflect the desired algorithm properties described in assessment aim(s) (see above). State which metric(s) were used to compute the ranking(s) (if any).

- Example 1: Dice Similarity Coefficient (DSC)
- Example 2: Area under curve (AUC)

Following established report generation challenges (VLM3D), the evaluation utilizes a combination of Natural Language Generation (NLG) and clinical accuracy metrics to provide a multi-faceted assessment of model performance:

(1) NLG & Factuality Metrics: BLEU (1-4), METEOR, and ROUGE are used to evaluate linguistic fluency, semantic similarity, and content completeness. In addition to these standard metrics, we employ state-of-the-art clinically-aware metrics to penalize hallucinations: (a) RadGraph-XL: A graph-based metric that evaluates the factual correctness of extracted clinical entities and relations, ensuring the generated report's clinical graph aligns with the ground truth. (b) Green: A learning-based metric specifically trained to identify clinically significant errors and hallucinations in radiology reports, providing a robust measure of generation safety.

(2) Clinical Accuracy Metrics: Precision, Recall (Sensitivity), and F1 Score are calculated by extracting abnormality labels from the generated reports to ensure the model correctly identifies pathologies across the five organs of interest. To mitigate error propagation from the extraction process, the LLM-based label extractor was validated on a held-out subset. It achieved a 4.5/5 concordance rate with manual labels annotated by board-certified radiologists.

The final ranking is computed using a point-based system inspired by the BraTS and VerSe challenges. This involves calculating metrics for all test images, conducting a two-sided unpaired permutation test with 10,000 permutations to evaluate statistical significance between teams, and allocating points based on pairwise comparisons where one team outperforms another

b) Justify why the metric(s) was/were chosen, preferably with reference to the biomedical application.

These metrics are widely adopted for evaluating the accuracy of radiology report generation. Relying solely on NLG metrics is insufficient, as scores can remain high even if generated reports lack clinical accuracy due to models overfitting to specific sentence structures rather than understanding pathological content. By integrating a combination of NLG and clinical metrics (Precision, Recall, F1), the evaluation ensures a comprehensive assessment of a model's ability to detect clinically relevant abnormalities while balancing sensitivity, specificity, and overall linguistic reliability.

Ranking method(s)

a) Describe the method used to compute a performance rank for all submitted algorithms based on the generated metric results on the test cases. Typically the text will describe how results obtained per case and metric are aggregated to arrive at a final score/ranking. Ideally, provide the ranking scheme as a concrete pseudo code.

The final leaderboard is determined using a point-based ranking system that first ranks algorithms on individual cases and then aggregates the results. The process follows these steps: (1) Metric Computation: Calculate the relevant evaluation metrics for all test images to assess the performance of each algorithm; (2) Statistical Analysis: For each metric, conduct a two-sided unpaired permutation test with 10,000 permutations per test image to evaluate the statistical significance of performance differences between teams; (3) Point Allocation: Assign a "total point count" to each team based on the number of pairwise comparisons in which they statistically outperform others ; and (4) Final Aggregation: Use the total point counts to determine the final ranking of the participating teams. This structured approach ensures a fair and statistically robust evaluation that is stable against outlier performances. To ensure that clinical correctness is prioritized over linguistic fluency, the calculated points are aggregated such that Clinical Accuracy metrics (F1, Precision, Recall) contribute 70% to the final ranking score, while Natural Language Generation (NLG) metrics (BLEU, METEOR, ROUGE, Green, RadGraph-XL) contribute 30%.

b) Describe the method(s) used to manage submissions with missing results on test cases.

An implicit penalty for both the Natural Language Generation (NLG) and clinical accuracy metrics is enforced. For the clinical accuracy evaluation, missing abnormality labels are automatically penalized within the classification scoring framework

c) Justify why the described ranking scheme(s) was/were used.

This ranking scheme is selected because comparable methodologies employed in the VLM3D, BraTS, Medical Segmentation Decathlon, VerSe'19, and VerSe'20 challenges have been highly regarded by participants for their consistency and stability in managing outlier results.

Statistical analyses

Provide an overview of the statistical approaches used in the scope of the challenge analysis. Details can be provided in the parameters below. For each parameter, justify why the described statistical method(s) was/were used and, if necessary, add a description of any method used to assess whether the data met the assumptions required for the particular statistical approach.

The evaluation uses a two-sided unpaired permutation test to determine the statistical significance of metric differences between algorithms.

Provide a description of how the precision of the performance estimates of individual algorithms is assessed (e.g. confidence interval of the mean on the test set computed using percentile bootstrap, confidence interval of the accuracy on the test set computed using percentile bootstrap).

By analyzing the metric values as a sample of the distribution, the evaluation ensures that the reported rankings are statistically robust and stable against outlier performances.

Provide a description of how variability of the performance of individual algorithms across tests cases is assessed (e.g. SD across test cases, IQR, graphs, reporting outliers...).

To assess the stability of participating algorithms, we will report the Standard Deviation (SD) and Interquartile Range (IQR) for all primary metrics (Clinical F1, BLEU-4) across the test set.

Provide a description of how variability of rankings is assessed.

N/A

Provide a description of statistical tests that are used to assess whether the differences in performance between algorithms are statistically significant.

N/A

Provide a description of the missing data handling.

If an algorithm fails to generate a report for a valid test case (e.g., runtime error, timeout, or empty output), that case will be assigned the worst possible score (0) for all metrics. This strict penalty ensures that highly ranked models are not only accurate but also robust enough for real-world clinical deployment.

Indicate any software product that is used for all data analysis methods.

N/A

Further analyses

Present further analyses to be performed (if applicable), e.g. related to

- combining algorithms via ensembling,
- inter-algorithm variability,
- common problems/biases of the submitted methods, or
- ranking variability.

N/A

ADDITIONAL POINTS

References

Please include any reference important for the challenge design, for example publications on the data, the annotation process or the chosen metrics as well as DOIs referring to data or code.

N/A

Further comments

Further comments from the organizers.

N/A